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PHYSICAL INTERPRETATION OF EFFICIENCY IN THE USE OF HYDROGEN ENERGY.

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Annotation. In this article, storage processes in hydrogen energy, physical parameters in the use of hydrogen and the level of efficiency were analyzed. The structure, principles of operation and useful aspects of the devices used in hydrogen energy were explained.

Key words. Hydrogen energy, thermodynamic potential, high thermal conductivity, low viscosity, liquefied gas.

Introduction. Scientists are studying theoretical and practical ways to use hydrogen energy, the world's leading countries have developed long-term strategies to build a hydrogen-powered economy, and many of them have already begun to be implemented [1,7]. Hydrogen energy is also known as the energy obtained from substances containing hydrogen or the element hydrogen. The use of hydrogen energy in various sectors of the economy is being introduced. The use of hydrogen energy is important in the chemical industry, petroleum products, energy, metallurgy, radio engineering, aerospace, as well as in the prevention of global warming and the replacement of other types of energy. Hydrogen is used as a fuel or fuel product. The hydrogen obtained by electrolyzing water into hydrogen and oxygen gases is called environmentally friendly green hydrogen. First you need to store it in order to use hydrogen. Special containers for hydrogen storage were produced. New methods of hydrogen energy storage are currently being tested and the computer is being technologically modeled (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Hydrogen energy storage. Experimental analysis and modeling.

Although new types of energy are expected to be found, hydrogen energy is now seen as a promising sector. Energy is definitely a big problem in an era where science and technology are advancing. It is important to meet the needs of society through energy supply and to organize the technological aspects of stabilizing this energy supply. At present, electric cars have replaced cars running on gasoline, gas and other fuels. This is a great achievement because environmental pollution is prevented. Despite the high cost of hydrogen, there are prospects. Despite the fact that this field is still young, there are many innovations in the field. This research is being conducted by more developed countries, especially the United States and Japan. Experts of our country also have proposals and plans in this regard.

Methods. In order to develop a fully operational hydrogen energy system, it is first necessary to identify a potential hydrogen energy market for all relevant technologies. This task is not always easy, especially since most of the technologies used in hydrogen power systems are still in the market entry stage. Nevertheless, the possibilities of using hydrogen as a fuel show that it is suitable for many promising applications and is effective in real life, safe for hydrogen and widely used in end use. In addition, the diversity of hydrogen provides a basis for assessing

the needs of the hydrogen energy market. The American Institute of Chemical Engineers (AIChE) expects that the main directions of future use of hydrogen energy will depend mainly on the following 4 elements:

- current and future costs of hydrogen power systems;
- the level of development of various technologies of the hydrogen power system;
- current and future costs of alternative energy systems;
- effects of hot gases and emissions on current and future climates.

Hydrogen can become a much-needed fuel for the transportation industry. On the other hand, in order to have a stable and long-term market for hydrogen energy that can meet the needs of the transport sector, it is necessary to address many technological elements that primarily affect the cost of vehicles and fuel. It would be very beneficial to use hydrogen as a fuel in order to minimize the cost of electric vehicles. Although fuel prices have fallen significantly, especially in the last two years, their economic performance has been an important driver for hydrogen energy markets, including battery-powered electric vehicles, including current or future alternative solutions. depends on. If rechargeable electric vehicles work efficiently at a low cost, users will prefer to purchase rechargeable electric vehicles over other hydrogen-powered vehicles. As a result, the desire to support the transition to hydrogen-powered vehicles may decrease.

An additional and very important element influencing the hydrogen energy market in the transport sector is the availability of hydrogen compared to other low-emission alternative fuels, such as biofuels. is a shortage of gas emissions. In the field of transport, biofuels could potentially become the most economical, clean, reliable and efficient alternative to conventional fossil fuel transportation as a result of the expansion of the hydrogen energy market. The potential success of biologically based fuels is due to their ease of production, delivery and use. In addition, biofuels may not require a major overhaul of the infrastructure. The main industries that use hydrogen are: the chemical industry, automobiles and housing.

Table 1 compares the energy consumption of vehicles running on compressed gas and cryogenic liquid hydrogen relative to propane and gasoline. Here it can be seen that a large amount of energy is needed to compress hydrogen to the required working pressure in the gas phase. For comparative evaluation, the vehicle selected here is powered by a diesel-powered compression-fueled engine.

Parameter	H_2 (gas)	H_2 (liquid)	Propane	Gasoline
Working pressure (MPa)	20	0.1	0.5	0.1
Required weight (kg)	40,000	30,000	40,000	40,000
Delivered weight (kg)	400	2,100	20,000	14,000
Minimum heating cost (MJ) of delivered fuel	120	120	46.3	44.8
Minimum heating value of energy for a truck (GJ)	48	252	926	1,164.8
When consuming diesel fuel (kg)	79.6	57.9	60	54
Minimum heating value of diesel (GJ)	3.38	2.46	2.55	2.30
Energy consumption relative to gasoline (unmeasured)	35.77	4.96	1.40	1.00

Table 1. Comparison of energy consumption in road transport with hydrogen propane and gasoline.

There are the following factors that encourage the use of hydrogen energy:

1. The production of solar and wind energy is environmentally friendly, including carbon, because it uses fossil fuels in mining. Even in the production of equipment for this energy using cheaper solar energy, its energy is much more expensive, and such energy can be available only in the presence of subsidies. And any energy storage systems will increase that cost.
2. Hydropower and geothermal energy resources are limited and almost exhausted. Due to the use of fossil fuels in the construction of a single hydropower plant, a large amount of carbon is used.
3. Additional problems related to nuclear energy or other alternative energy sources and nuclear waste, including related accidents, increase the importance of hydrogen.
4. It is noteworthy that hydrogen can occupy a small volume. In the following table, we consider the required size in the example of four different wind generators:

Wind Generator Power (MW)	1	5	1	5
Daily energy reserve (MW*h)	24	120		
5 day energy reserve			120	600
H_2 amount	600	3000	3000	15000
H_2 normal density (kg / m^3)	≈ 0	≈ 0	≈ 0	≈ 0
Normal H_2 size (m^3)	6 667	33 333	33 333	166 667
200 atm pressure H_2 capacity (m^3)	33	167	167	833

Ball radius (m) for storage at a pressure of 200 atm	2	3	3	6
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Table 2. Physical performance of hydrogen in four wind turbines.

Results. In modern technological processes, 200 atm is the perfect working pressure. If we look at human energy consumption not from the point of view of environmental problems, but from the point of view of real problems, then we are convinced that the only problem that threatens human civilization is the reduction of economically viable hydrocarbons and coal.

Hydrogen can be burned directly (in internal combustion engines, boilers of thermal power plants, etc.). Direct fuel combustion is unlikely to be widely used due to the tendency of hydrogen to explode. Attempts were made in the United States in 1944 to use hydrogen as rocket fuel, but this idea was eventually abandoned due to the slightest unpredictable explosions. Of course, such negative aspects do not mean that we should give up hydrogen. Today, the rapid development of technology is paving the way for the discovery of new methods of using resources. Such methods can further increase the efficiency of hydrogen use.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of fuel cells:

H_2 -hydrogen molecule; H- hydrogen atoms; H^+ - proton; e^- - electron; O-oxygen atom; O_2 - oxygen molecules; H_2O - water molecule; 1- external electric circuit; 2- hydrogen chambers; 3 - anode (catalytic layer); 4- membrane (solid field electrolyte); 5- cathode (catalytic layer); 6 - oxygen chamber; 7 - oxygen-enriched air; 8 - used hydrogen; 9 - oxygen-treated air = $2H_2O + O$. In this case, the chemical energy of the reagents in the combustion reaction (hydrogen and oxygen) is completely transferred only to the proton [4].

Discussion. Practically all national "hydrogen" programs provide for the use of fuel cells as the main source of hydrogen energy. Knowledge of the general principles of operation of fuel cells is becoming an integral part of modern technical culture of mankind. Let's analyze the process in Figure 2. We see this principle in the example of a solid polymer electrolyte fuel cell. The unit element form of such an element. The fuel cell consists of an anode (hydrogen electrode) and a cathode (oxygen electrode). The anode and cathode are separated by a solid polymer electrolyte in the form of a membrane. The fuel is hydrogen gas introduced into the anode zone. The anode contains a platinum catalyst, as a result of which hydrogen molecules are adsorbed on the surface of the catalyst and first decompose into atoms, then atoms into positively charged protons and negatively charged electrons. The most important feature of a solid polymer membrane is that only positively charged protons can enter the cathode. Accordingly, excess electrons accumulate in the hydrogen electrolyte (anode), from which protons are released and it is negatively charged.

Conversely, an oxygen electrode (cathode) forms protons and is positively charged. In other words, the potential difference occurs between the anode and cathode. Therefore, when an external circuit containing voltage is closed, an electric current flows in it, which can do useful work. In the presence of a catalyst, the electrons entering the cathode during the flow deliver the reaction of water formation from protons passing through the membrane and the oxygen supplied to the cathode from the outside. Let us also remember that the direct combustion of hydrogen

produces water as a result of a chemical combustion reaction. The reaction of water formation in fuel cells is different. Here, hydrogen oxidation occurs as an electrochemical reaction, and as a result, most of the chemical energy of the reagents (theoretically 83%) is converted directly into heat energy. Thus, fuel cells are a very efficient source of electricity and, in addition, a source of low-level heat. The most important component of fuel electricity, only partial elements, are usually platinum catalysts in the carbon carrier. The cost of platinum catalysts is about 30% of the cost of the fuel cell. For each kW of fuel cell power consumes 1 g of platinum metals.

It is estimated that in the future the global fuel cell industry will require about 180-200 tons of platinum or other platinum metals. In the United States, new catalysts based on nanotechnology using an alloy of platinum with cobalt and copper have been developed, which are much cheaper and 5 times more efficient. The voltage at which a separate fuel cell appears does not exceed 1.1 V. The batteries are connected in series to obtain the desired voltage value. Such fuel cells, together with thermal control valves, are assembled into a single structural unit called an electrochemical generator. There are different types of fuel cells.

Conclusions. In conclusion, the most common classification by type of electrolysis with the means of internal conductivity of protons:

- Solid oxide fuel cells;
- Proton exchange membrane fuel cells;
- Renewable fuel cells;
- Direct methanol fuel cell;
- Dissolved carbonate fuel cell;
- Phosphorus fuel cell.

Hydrogen energy is not yet widely used, as a clear methodology for the production, storage and transportation of hydrogen has not yet been developed, but various developments and laboratory studies are at a promising stage. Other advantages of hydrogen include its very high thermodynamic properties (thermodynamic potential is 143.06 MJ/kg), high thermal conductivity and low viscosity.

Hydrogen is transported smoothly in pipes because of its low viscosity. Hydrogen is stored as a liquefied gas. Hydrogen has a long life and is very light. Modern technologies of hydrogen energy allow to obtain high-quality fuel material with high thermal conductivity. This energy carrier has a wide range of applications: in industrial economics, housing and communal services (heating of residential buildings). Hydrogen energy is safe for the environment. Hydrogen can be used as a fuel for internal combustion engines (it is more efficient than gasoline or diesel fuel); when heated, it does not emit carbine anhydride, i.e. it has a less negative effect on the atmosphere. Today, many industrial companies are working to create cheap hydrogen fuel cells. Many theoretical works on interrelationship between hydrogen energy and other subjects (for example, hydrogen energy and superconductivity) are being learned [2,3,5,6,7,8].

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